

**ART OR THE LINGUOPOETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE
TRANSLATED WORK
(BASED ON THE TRANSLATIONS OF "THE ALCHEMIST")**

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Abstract. Literary literature as a type of art draws human thoughts and imaginations to the scope of vision and gaze precisely due to images, and depicts a person in literary works with all his goals and intentions, image and character. It is precisely because of such advantages that literary literature is considered the "crown of art" and it has gained educational, moral, ideological and aesthetic value due to its image.

Key words: fiction, art, translation, literary translation, image, linguo poetics, linguo poetic analysis, language of a work of art.

Artistic literature is an artistic perception of existence, a unique type of speech activity of mankind, and one of the modern directions of linguistics - linguo poetics has a special place in the research and study of its linguistic features. The analysis of the language of a work of art is of great importance from the linguo poetic point of view.

Among the various types of art, fiction is distinguished by its own characteristics. The reason for this is that the images of fiction cannot be directly felt, seen or heard. A person directly sees architecture, painting, dance, and hears music and songs. When reading a story, reciting a ghazal, a person tries to understand the meanings hidden in them. Only after that he imagines the artistic image - scenes of human life.

The world of existence is one with all its details. In order to reach the full and ripe conclusions of life, along with scientific intelligence, a high-flying artistic imagination is also necessary. Because science studies the objective legitimacy of the world of

existence, and the artist accepts this legitimacy as a basis, makes it effective and rich through imagery. This is why scientific findings in fiction become even more complete and pleasant. In this sense, the task of the artist is not to prove the truth, but to show it in images. Hegel called this process "art is thinking through images".

In fact, fiction, which is historically formed as a form of public consciousness, serves great and noble human purposes. As we can see in the best classical works of the world, the writers have fulfilled the special duties of anthropology and humanism with their works. In this sense, literature is a school of humanity. Man in literature is not only the main subject and object of the image, but also its sole purpose. Education of human feelings and thoughts, his character and artistic taste is the main intention of true artists. Therefore, human interest in the world of beauty, which is fully expressed in works of art, is a conscious action that is guided by the idea of man.

Linguistics belongs equally to literature and language and is a part of philological research, focused on the study of artistic and aesthetic properties of the text. Linguistics is the language of a work of art or a set of language tools used in a work of art to express the purpose and idea of the creator. To put it simply, the language of a work of art is the subject of linguistics.

The history of mankind is full of examples of people who were always followed by misfortune and chaos, but later the light of success surrounded them. In particular, if you read related books and literature, you will witness how many people have reached the safe shore with the will and solidarity of those around them, and have become real leaders or pioneers. And one of the main subtleties in the way of advancement is to be an inspirational figure for others. Most of the people who are considered leaders by the people, say: "Leadership is not our personal success, but the success of those whom we have inspired." In other words, a leader does not appear by himself, but is nurtured by the environment. And one cannot exist without the other.

The literary-aesthetic effect of any work of art does not depend on what the text is about, but on how it is expressed. Determining how this or that linguistic unit is used

by the author in the process of artistic creation, what kind of aesthetic effect this or that combination of words gives, determines the purpose of linguopoetic analysis.

The writer Paulo Coelho in one of his works "The Alchemist" tells the story of a young shepherd named Santiago who travels to the desert to find a great treasure. After long journeys and many difficulties, Santiago reaches his destination, but not as expected, but better than that. In fact, we, like Santiago, are searching for treasure, searching for meaning in life in the wilderness and our personal problems. The search for such treasures can be material, or it can be spiritual, regardless of this purpose, there is no substitute. And in the course of this adventure, we imagine ourselves as a hero who can change the course of the world with a dream and a strong will and guide it towards creativity. Such a desire is natural, because a person lives as long as he is active!

The issue of the interrelationship of linguistic tools and their aesthetic activation in the context of literary literature is extremely important for the complete philological understanding of the literary text. Although semantic, metasemiotic and linguopoetic level units are involved in the aesthetic formation of the text, the word plays a major role as the main unit of the language; all the remaining units and other elements of the interpretation of the terms of literary science are gathered around it. Without completely denying the importance of other language units, it is possible to emphasize the nuclear position of language in the formation of artistic impression.

A sign of a person's activity is his academic progress, sports achievements, his relationship with other members of society and professional success, such as the development of personal skills. And the true leader will show himself step by step in this process, and one day the society will accept him. A true leader never claims to be a leader. This can only be proven by the actions of such a person. Moving from individual contribution to the role of leadership, the leader realizes that one of the characteristics of this position is the ability to follow the people of society. However,

if you limit your leadership skills to the ability to command and command, then one day you will surely fail.

Also in this way until the establishment of the process of personal thinking and stabilization of material-spiritual values, ideological and moral difficulties arise. That is why it is important to build moral and intellectual standards on moral and universal values at the beginning of the road. Because every leader has a tendency to carry out his own desires. That is, at the beginning of the road, carnal desires may play a role above the common good, or on the contrary, at the end of the road, he becomes drunk and intoxicated with power and power and loses his humanity completely. In both cases, the emptiness of spiritual and universal values is revealed and they testify that such a leader has no dreams beyond his sensuality from the beginning of his career.

Therefore, in order not to be seduced by the abyss of carnal desires as a leader, adopt the system of consulting competent people and asking advice from business people at the beginning of the journey and follow this system until the end of the journey. Surround yourself with positive people and avoid "toxic" habits. Because together with the environment, people around you, family members, colleagues and peers and the society itself, you create a "whole spiritual person", thus you pass from the narrow circle of "I" to the blessed period of "we". This kind of transition to constructive change will be the factor and basis of success and the formation of a true leading personality.

The literary text not only reflects the real existence, but also constitutes the substance of the world creatively created in the artistic work. The word created by the author, conditioned by the artistic task assigned to him, becomes richer in terms of aesthetic content, begins to live with the laws of complex aesthetic integrity. The word appears in all its colors and becomes a tool of figurative thinking. Therefore, when understanding a word in a literary text, it should not be forgotten that it acts on at least three different levels at the same time. Therefore, the word artist itself can be the object of three types of analysis. Semantic and metasemiotic analyzes belong to the field of

linguistics, and the content of meaning is limited only by covering the semantics of words and their emotional-expressive meanings and evaluating them, in other words, connotations. Therefore, when understanding a word in a literary text, it should not be forgotten that it acts on at least three different levels at the same time. Therefore, the artistic word itself can be the object of three types of analysis. Semantic and metasemiotic analyzes belong to the field of linguistics, and the content of meaning is limited only by covering the semantics of words and their emotional-expressive meanings and evaluating them, in other words, connotations. Therefore, when understanding a word in a literary text, it should not be forgotten that it acts on at least three different levels at the same time. Therefore, the artistic word itself can be the object of three types of analysis. Semantic and metasemiotic analyzes belong to the field of linguistics, and the content of meaning is limited only by covering the semantics of words and their emotional-expressive meanings and evaluating them, in other words, connotations.

The Alchemist is perhaps the best known personal development novel in the world. It tells the story of a boy who goes from Andalusia to Morocco to change his life and follow his treasure.

"Why didn't you tell the story about the Way of Santiago," the pilgrim said to the traveler when the two of them left the conference. "As far as I'm concerned, many pilgrims try to walk all the way, regardless of whether they are on the Way of Santiago or on the way of life. At the beginning of my visit, I tried to walk like my group. I was full, I demanded more than possible from my body. My attention increased, the flesh of my left leg became swollen. I couldn't walk for two days, and I realized that I could reach Santiago only if I walked at my own pace. This left me far away from others, I walked the long way alone. But because of this incident, I started to respect the speed with which I managed to cover the entire road. I used this style in my life."

When understanding the third level, lingupoetic (level, layer), more complex and subtle aesthetic features of the word are encountered; are related to the ideological-

artistic content of the work of art. Lingupoetic analysis has a universal character, it can be applied to any literary speech, regardless of its style. The general feature of this method of analysis does not distinguish between the literary texts involved in the analysis, it sees them on the same level. However, it is the lingupoetic analysis that makes it possible to clarify and justify the role of the literary text as an example of verbal art.

The text tells the journey of Santiago, a young shepherd, in search of the treasure of the Egyptian pyramids. On his journey through the desert, he learns the basic concepts of his existence due to successive encounters with various enigmatic characters. Key among them is the teachings of alchemists, who, after revealing all their power, make the hero's life eternal.

The main character is Santiago, an experienced Andalusian shepherd in search of his special fairy tale. Then the cowardly ghouls appear, but he becomes the key to interpreting the hero's vision. Then Melchizedek (King Salim), a merchant, Fatima (with whom Santiago falls in love) and a powerful alchemist with a learned hunting skill appear.

Santiago, a sheep herder who is very comfortable with his nomadic lifestyle, goes on an unknown journey to find treasure. This was revealed to him only when he discovered the secrets of his ability to elevate his body, mind and soul. In order to discover these mystical signs, the hero must let go of all ego, develop his spirit and abandon any hint of vanity. Only then can he listen to the universe.

When Santiago asks the gypsies to explain his recurring dream of a boy who shows him a treasure in the Egyptian pyramids, he is at a loss for an explanation. For this reason, the juggler explains: "the simplest things in life are the most extraordinary, and only the wise see them."

The hero vainly suggests that he forget his vision (and the call of his destiny). But an old man in Arabic dress - Melchizedek - reminds him of the mistake of fate. The old

man tells him: "at some point in our lives we lose control of what happens to us and our lives are ruled by faith."

Santiago is torn between a normal, familiar life and an adventure full of uncertainty. Melchizedek urges him to continue his search; If things don't work out, you can go back to the pastor. The old man becomes the king of Salim. After he reveals his true identity, he gives Santiago a small black and white stone with the intention of helping him with his symptoms. Although he emphasizes the importance of "making up your own mind"

Once in Africa, Santiago was tricked by a merchant and stole his money. Then, the hero must choose how to approach the situation. That is, if you see yourself as a victim or a cheater. However, he decides on a better option: to think that he is an adventurer in search of treasure.

After a year working as a window cleaner, Santiago saves enough money to return to his old life as a shepherd. But the employer knows what the young man will decide because it is "written" (in the hands of God). Santiago does not buy a sheep, he continues to search for his dream, because the signs of the universe are clear.

Santiago falls in love with Fatima, a young woman from a caravan crossing the Sahara. The feeling is mutual, but she invites him to pursue his dream and promises to wait for him at the oasis. In the midst of grief over the eventual separation, Santiago sees a vision of some warriors attacking the oasis. Thanks to that prophecy, the Cacique and his tribe saved themselves.

Love never gets in the way of personal legend. Santiago realizes this concept after meeting a character imbued with mystical powers. It is about a chemist who was waiting for him and explains the three types of chemistry. The former tries to grow and evolve together with its environment to reach the so-called philosopher's stone.

The second type of alchemist finds their gift almost by accident, when they stumble upon it, when their souls are ready to take on this role. The third type of alchemist shows only the temptation of gold, so he can never find the "secret". The

teacher always refers to the simple things because "all the things you have to learn along the way".

When a military expedition kidnaps Santiago and the alchemist, the latter pretends to be only a guide and predicts that his chamber will turn into a storm in three days. In the first stage, Santiago doubts himself; later he manages to speak to the elements and the universe, begging to meet his beloved. Finally, the combination of sand, wind, sky and space turns Santiago into a hurricane.

An alchemist teaches Santiago to turn lead into gold. When a young man comes to the pyramids of Egypt, he sees a scarab burying himself in sand and interprets it as a sign of the universe. He starts digging for treasure until he is ambushed by a group of war refugees. They take all the gold from Santiago and read to tell about his dream.

But the leader of the refugees tells him a dream of his own. In the leader's vision, there was a treasure hidden under the roots of a sycamore tree near the ruins, a sacrifice that the sheep often visited. For this reason, the former shepherd returns to the place where it all began two years ago in Spain. There he takes a chest with gold coins. Finally, the wind brings him a familiar perfume... Santiago is already walking towards his beloved.

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